

Gibb's Paradox, Interaction States and Quantum Mechanics?

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Gibb's Paradox is associated with introducing a $1/N!$ factor in the partition function $= 1/N! \{ \text{Sum over } i \exp(-e_i/T) \}$ power N (1). It is often stated that $N!$ is required to deal with identical particles. It is further stated that in classical physics, particles have an identity, but in quantum mechanics, they are identical and so the $N!$ is really a quantum mechanical feature.

In (2), we argued that $dE=TdS - PdV$ is entirely focused on interactions and so if $S = -k \ln(\text{number of states})$, one should consider interaction states, not identity states. We argued that a green particle differs in colour from a red one, but this has nothing to do with interactions and one would completely ignore colour when calculating the number of states. The same reasoning applies to two identifiably different particles with the same e, p being at x_1 , and x_2 versus x_2 , x_1 . In terms of identity states, there are two, but they both represent the same physical interaction and are counted once. Even though classical particles have an identity, and quantum ones also because they have a center-of-mass, from the point of view of an interaction, a particle at (x, y, z) with a certain momentum and energy is all that one needs to know for interaction purposes. It is irrelevant which particle is at this (x, y, z) and so $N!$ is introduced for this reason, as argued in (2).

Here we consider the quantum mechanical case. We have argued in previous notes that quantum mechanics follows from special relativity. In particular, a particle still has a center-of-mass and so an identity. If it moves with constant speed, one has the classical equation $x=vt$ for the center-of-mass. This begs the question: Where are the quantum mechanical features? We argue they are in the interaction. The fact that the center-of-mass is at some x, t does not mean that a p (momentum) impulse hit is rendered at that point. In fact, the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$, which is more general than $x=vt$, may be considered to be a kind of free particle potential with x, t and $x+h\bar{v}/p$, $t+h\bar{v}/E$ having the same potential values and rendering the same hit, regardless of whether $x=vt$. $-Et+px$ is already created using the notion $x=vt$ for the center-of-mass and so $-Et+px$ holds for more x, t points than simply $x=vt$. As a result, the quantum free particle wavefunction $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ represents a probability to interact, not a center-of-mass identity of the particle. In other words, quantum mechanics is a statistical theory of interaction and as such the probability bypasses the actual position of the center-of-mass which identifies the particle.

In a 2-slit experiment, a particle has a specific center-of-mass and moves as $x=vt$, but at the 2-slit apparatus (with slits about $h\bar{v}/p$ apart), it may probabilistically interact with both slits. This is a probabilistic interaction calculation which has little to do with the center-of-mass position and hence any position identity of the particle. As a result, a more general quantum wavefunction $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ (bound state) is also an interaction probability. Thus, quantum mechanics automatically only considers interactions and this leads some to argue that there is no particle identity in quantum mechanics. We argue that just like classical physics, there is a particle identity (center-of-mass), but the interaction is the main focus and does not depend on this identity position. In other words, one only deals with interaction probabilities, just like classical statistical mechanical problems should only deal with interaction states (as argued in (2)), and not with any physical state which may be identified, but does not change the interaction. The difference between quantum mechanics and classical mechanics, is

that quantum mechanics is formulated on the notion of interaction (so the particle identity is removed from the calculation right away), while in the classical case one retains the identity and has to manually correct for identity states in order to convert the number to the number of interaction states.

Gibb's Paradox and Interaction States

In (2), we argued that the first law of thermodynamics:

$$dE = TdS - PdV \quad ((1))$$

focuses entirely on interactions. dE occurs only if there are interactions as does PdV . As a result, TdS must be based on interactions as well. Given Boltzmann's definition:

$$S = -k \ln(\text{number of states}) \quad ((2)),$$

we argue that one cannot consider any physical state, but only different interaction states. This leads to the following situation. Consider $dE = PdV = 0$ and a box of size $2V$ with $2N$ particles. If one introduces a partition so that N particles are in one V with T and the other N in the other V with T , then $dS = 0$. If one wishes S to be extensive, then one has a problem with physical states because each of the $2N$ particles in $2V$ may be at any position, whereas each of the $2N$ particles in the partition case are restricted to positions in a size V . Clearly, if physical states are considered, then one does not have the \ln of the product of the volume states in the partition case equaling the \ln of the volume states in the $2V$ case. This, however, is irrelevant, as argued in (2), because all one is interested in is interactions. It does not matter that the N particles in V are restricted to V . The question is whether the interaction possibilities for the partition case match those of the $2V$ case and they do because T is the same in both V compartments. This, we argue, is why one introduces the $N!$ Factor to deal with the Gibb's paradox and this argument does not require any knowledge of quantum mechanics.

This begs the question: Why does one see in the literature statements to the effect that some believe the $N!$ factor is due to quantum mechanics (3)? We argue that quantum mechanics is a probabilistic theory based solely on interaction. The quantum free particle wavefunction (probability) $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ already removes the notion of particle identity (center-of-mass position) and thus dealing with a wavefunction makes it appear as if the quantum particle does not have an identity. We argue that it does, but that this identity is not particularly involved in a probabilistic interaction calculation. Given that it does not appear in such a calculation (e.g. 2-slit calculation), it is assumed that quantum particles are identical and that $N!$ follows for this reason, which we refute.

Quantum Mechanics and Indistinguishability of Particles

We argue that classical particles have an identity in space because one can follow their center-of-mass motion. A particle with constant speed moves as:

$$x=vt \quad ((3))$$

We argue that ((3)) holds for a quantum particle's center-of-mass as well. An electron produced at some point moves in a straight line according to ((3)) until it reaches a 2-slit apparatus with slit separation of about \hbar/p . At the 2-slit apparatus, one must focus on a possible interaction. Classically, the interaction of the particle is based at its center-of-mass, i.e. if it arrives at a slit it passes through, otherwise it strikes the solid material. Quantum mechanics, on the other hand, does not restrict interactions to the center-of-mass point. Rather, they may occur probabilistically within $\hbar/p = dx$. This means that there is a probability for an interaction with both slits and one adds probabilities in an OR situation. In particular, the probability is $\exp(-iEt+i p \cdot r)$, but one may drop $\exp(-iEt)$ in the calculation. Then:

$$\text{Wavefunction} = \exp(i p \cdot r_1) + \exp(i p \cdot r_2) \quad ((4a))$$

Each probability has the same weight factor because neither slit has any bias. R_1 is a vector from slit one (center) to a point on a screen far away and r_2 is a vector from the center of the second slit to the same point on the screen. One multiplies ((4)) by its complex conjugate to get a spatial probability distribution in x at the screen. ((4)) is a probabilistic calculation which is based entirely on the interaction. Physically, an electron has an identity and center-of-mass, but this does not predict what happens when it interferes. Rather, it is ((4)) which gives probabilities which make sense if one considers an ensemble. A single particle will simply change its p direction and move to some x point on the screen. Given that ((4)) automatically deals with an interaction and not with position identity of the center-of-mass, quantum mechanics, which deals with probabilistic calculations using the wavefunction (probability object).

Thus, we argue that quantum mechanical calculations directly use a wavefunction which is a probability only concerned with interactions. This is why indistinguishability is enforced on the wavefunction. In particular, if one has two quantum particles, given that only the interaction is of concern, one would write:

$$\text{Wavefunction} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \{ |\text{particle 1}\rangle|\text{state1}\rangle |\text{particle 2}\rangle|\text{state2}\rangle \pm |\text{particle 2}\rangle|\text{state1}\rangle |\text{particle 1}\rangle|\text{state2}\rangle \} \quad ((4b))$$

((4b)) reflects the indistinguishability of the interaction, not the particle. The center-of-mass of the particle which distinguishes it, is not part of the probability calculation based on the wavefunction. Thus, quantum mechanics a priori forces one to only include interaction states.

This, we argue, is why some people state that quantum particles are indistinguishable. It is the interaction which does make use of their distinguishability as it has nothing to do with the interaction, just as in the classical two volume partition situation. The indistinguishability is not some special quantum mechanical property of a particle, we argue.

In the next section, we try to show how the quantum interaction probability arises and its relation to $x=vt$, i.e. center-of-mass motion.

$x=vt$ and $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$

A classical particle is distinguishable and moves according to $x=vt$. This implies that one may measure x and t with infinite resolution without disturbing the classical particle. A quantum particle, however, more or less moves as $x=vt$, as argued in the above section, but interacts in a strange manner. How does this come about?

In previous notes, we have argued that $x=vt$ is used to derive special relativity, but the key is that $x=vt$ only applies to the center-of-mass of a particle, its identity, while special relativity (Lorentz transformations) affect (x,t) as well as (p,E) . The latter are interaction variables and so we argue that special relativity is much more general than $x=vt$. In particular, one has the Lorentz invariant

$$-Et+px \quad ((5))$$

This is not $x=vt \rightarrow x=p/E t$ (for $c=1$ and a particle with rest mass). It should represent some different physics. One may choose a t value and then use $x=vt$ in ((5)). This is certainly the case, but $x+h\bar{p}/p$ and $t+h\bar{E}/E$ give the same value of ((5)). We have suggested that ((5)) is akin to the potential created by the particle. In other words, momentum hits do not necessarily occur at the center-of-mass point as in Newtonian mechanics. Rather, one has a probability expression $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ describing how interaction hits occur and these can deviate from the center-of-mass position (x,t) . As a result, a quantum calculation is based on these probabilities which do not distinguish the center-of-mass of the particles. This is how the notion of indistinguishability arises. It is the indistinguishability of the probabilistic interaction. In other words, it is the interaction which is key, and any distinguishable feature of a particle which does not affect the overall interaction is not included. As a result, one does not follow the center-of-mass in a 2-slit calculation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it is sometimes stated (3) that quantum particles are indistinguishable, whereas classical ones are not. As a result, one has to introduce an $N!$ by hand into a classical partition function to make the particles indistinguishable. It is sometimes suggested in the literature (see (3)) that such indistinguishability would appear naturally if one used quantum mechanics.

We argued in (2) that $S = -k \ln(\text{number of states})$ should only include states which represent different interactions. Even though two classical particles with the same p, e are distinguishable and so having 1 at x_1 and 2 at x_2 is different from 1 at $x_2, 2$ at x_1 , the interaction is not different. It is only the different interaction states which are of concern, we argued in (2). This has nothing to do with indistinguishability of particles.

This begs the question: What is happening in quantum mechanics? We argue that quantum particles have an identity too and center-of-mass. The catch is that they interact probabilistically according to $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ (probability for a free particle), so their center-of-mass identity is not key to a probabilistic calculation. This gives the appearance of quantum particles as being indistinguishable, but it is their role in an interaction which is indistinguishable, just as it is the classical ideal gas case.

References

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